
What's in a Scope? Where Neuropsychology Meets Clinical Psychology

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What is in a name? That which we call a rose, by any other name would smell as sweet.
William Shakespeare, Romeo and Juliet

Cognitive and psychometric testing has been a staple of clinical psychology practice almost since its inception, with clinical psychologists central to the development of formal psychometric tests for the US Army as early as 1914 (see Skirrow, 2020). The current 'core competencies' for clinical psychologists (New Zealand Psychologists Board, 2018) suggest that all of us should, at least, have:

- Knowledge of psychometric testing theory/practice, test construction and of the strengths and limitations of standardised tests.
- Knowledge of brain-behaviour relationships.
- (Skills in) Selection, administration and interpretation of psychometric measures relevant to area of practice.
- (Skills in) Completion of cognitive intellectual assessment and neuropsychological screening.

Before the establishment of the neuropsychologist scope of practice in 2018, the vast majority of neuropsychology work in New Zealand (particularly under Accident Compensation Corporation contracts) was traditionally undertaken by clinical psychologists. However, following the introduction of the scope, the Board recently expressed a concern that:

...this scope may be creating barriers to access for neuropsychology services by inadvertently downplaying the legitimate knowledge and expertise that clinical psychologists have in this area and causing uncertainty in the profession as to what, if any, neuropsychological work clinical psychologists can do. (New Zealand Psychologists Board, 2022)

The vast majority of psychologists that are registered in the neuropsychologist scope are also registered in the clinical psychology scope (167 of 179 psychologists according to the Board). However, since the 'grandparenting'¹ scheme ended in 2020, many of us have questioned how we might reasonably gain the skills required for registration, and in the meantime, what work is 'within our scope' as a clinical psychologist.

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¹ We use the term 'grandparenting' here, using the language employed by the Board, but must also note that the use of the term has raised some controversy given its roots in US racial discrimination law.

The Function of a Scope of Practice is to Protect the Public

Psychologists are registered under the Health Practitioners' Competency Assurance Act (2003), whose primary aim is *'to protect the health and safety of members of the public by providing mechanisms to ensure that health practitioners are competent and fit to practice their professions'*. In order to protect the public, the Board restricts the use of titles such as 'clinical psychologist' and 'neuropsychologist', so that you cannot legally claim to be something that you are not. For that reason, scopes of practice are designed to delineate a set of practices that are sufficiently distinct from those of other practitioners (in this case, other psychologists), that require additional skills and training, over and above those provided by foundational training courses.

Most of the comparable Western nations have formally recognised the profession of clinical neuropsychology and/or the title 'clinical neuropsychologist' for many years (e.g. Australia, the UK, the US, Canada, Germany, France, Italy). In some countries, such as the UK, clinical psychology is considered a foundation, with almost all neuropsychologists first undergoing clinical training. In others, including Australia, clinical neuropsychology represents an entirely separate training pathway². Despite the differing training pathways, there is consistent worldwide recognition that: a) clinical neuropsychology is distinct from usual (clinical) psychology practice; b) clinical neuropsychological practice requires a specific set of knowledge and skills that are not provided by clinical psychology training alone; and c) the consequences of substandard neuropsychological practice with vulnerable individuals who have neurological injury or illness can potentially have severe consequences.

With this in mind, there have been a number of proposals for the Board to consider the introduction of a neuropsychology scope of practice. A proposal made by several clinical neuropsychologists in the early 2000s was not successful. However, in 2015, 14 clinical psychologists working in the area of neuropsychology made a proposal to the Board to establish a 'clinical neuropsychology' scope of practice. After a lengthy period of consultation with the profession, including the development of what represents the core competencies, the scope was formally introduced in 2018. After an initial 13 months where psychologists could be grandparented¹ across to the new scope of practice on the basis of previous practice in neuropsychology, the deadline was extended for a further 2 years until March 2021. Since then, very few NZ clinical psychologists have been able to register within the neuropsychologist scope (regardless of whether they held the required competencies) as there has been no Board-accredited neuropsychology programme in New Zealand.

A Spectrum of Skill: From 'Clinical Psychologists' to 'Clinical Psychologists who do Neuropsychology' to 'Clinical Neuropsychologists'

The competencies needed to practice as a neuropsychologist are clearly defined in the New Zealand Psychologists Board core competencies document. Many clinical psychologists hold some of these competencies already, however it is unlikely that they will hold *all of them* without having undertaken additional practice or training in the area of neuropsychology. The focus of clinical psychology training, by necessity, tends to be broad and there is often relatively little time dedicated to practice in neuropsychology, so most clinicians will have developed these skills by themselves.

As we described above, the administering and scoring of cognitive tests, in the form of assessment of intellectual ability or cognitive 'screening', remain clearly within the scope and skill

² 'Clinical' can be considered to describe an approach, as in clinical psychology, or an applied setting, as in 'within a (hospital) clinic'.

of a (newly qualified) clinical psychologist, as defined by the Board. The Board's *Core Competencies for the Practice of Psychology in Aotearoa New Zealand* (2018) suggests that one of the key differences between a clinical psychologist and a neuropsychologist is a matter of the degree of knowledge and skill of the practitioner (see Table 1).

Table 1
Clinical Psychology Competencies versus Neuropsychologist Competencies

Clinical psychologist competency	Neuropsychologist competency
<i>Knowledge of psychometric testing theory/practice, test construction and of the strengths and limitations of standardised tests</i>	<i>Advanced knowledge of neuropsychological testing theory and practice, test construction and the strengths and limitations of standardised neuropsychological tests</i>
<i>Knowledge of brain-behaviour relationships</i>	<i>Advanced knowledge of brain-behaviour relationships</i>
<i>Selection, administration and interpretation of psychometric measures relevant to area of practice</i>	<i>Carefully considered selection of neuropsychological measures appropriate to the clinical setting and the reasons for referral; tailoring of neuropsychological assessment appropriate to the client and clinical hypotheses</i>

It is important to be clear that the competencies set by the Board represent the *minimum competencies required for registration* (i.e. they represent a level of knowledge expected of a newly qualified clinical psychologist). In terms of the neuropsychology scope, the Board does not explain exactly what constitutes an 'advanced' level knowledge; however, the wider competencies hint at several key areas where further training is likely to be needed beyond that offered by clinical psychology programmes.

First, the Board competencies speak to the level of *knowledge of cognitive tests and skill in test selection*. There are literally thousands of standardised and non-standardised cognitive tests available, each with their own relative strengths and weaknesses, as well as appropriate and inappropriate applications (Skirrow et al., *in preparation*). While administering a test largely involves following the test manual or instructions, the question of *which tests are appropriate to answer which referral questions* is likely to require a much greater range of knowledge.

Second, the Board competencies speak to the *interpretation of cognitive tests*. Assessing which neurological condition an individual is likely to be experiencing based on their symptomatology, behaviour and test profile is likely to require a much greater level of technical knowledge and interpretative skill than assessing whether they meet criteria for intellectual disability. Similarly, cognitive 'screening' tests are generally designed to measure whether (or not) a person is likely to have a cognitive impairment, without really being able to indicate *what is causing that impairment, or what interventions may be of benefit*.

Overall, the Board competencies suggest that (clinical) neuropsychologists are likely to require much greater level of knowledge of tests and test interpretation, as well as common neuropsychological, neurological and neuropsychiatric conditions. Neuropsychologists need to know much more about models of both normal and abnormal cognitive/neuropsychological functioning, as well as models of cognitive/neuropsychological rehabilitation. Furthermore, Neuropsychologists are likely to require a greater knowledge of the methods, terminology and

conceptual approaches of other professions, including neurologists, neuroradiologists and neurosurgeons. Table 2 presents some examples of simple versus complex referrals for neuropsychological assessment, the latter that we would suggest may be best left to psychologists with the ‘neuropsychologist’ scope of practice (and even then, under appropriate supervision).

Table 2
Complexity of Referral Questions for Neuropsychological Assessment

Simple referral questions <i>-Describing and quantifying a person’s impairment</i>	Complex referral questions <i>-Forming wider conclusions regarding the reasons for cognitive impairment, functional implications or treatment recommendations</i>
Does this person meet (cognitive) criteria for intellectual disability?	How much of this person’s impairment is related to their childhood head injury versus the neglect that they experienced while growing up?
Does this older person show significant cognitive deficits (relative to their peers)?	Is the person’s cognitive decline due to dementia and if so, which type of dementia are they likely to be experiencing?
What are this person’s cognitive strengths and weaknesses?	Is this person capable of work? If so, what kind of work? What supports will they need?
Does this person show significant cognitive difficulties (following their traumatic brain injury)?	Is this person’s cognitive impairment consistent with the reports of the mechanism and pathology of their injury? How would you formulate the combinations of injury, mood, personality and performance validity factors, to best understand their current functioning?

It is not Easy to End up ‘Out of Your Scope’ but it IS Easy to Slip Into Poor Practice

Despite the delineation of scopes by the Board and unlike more medical professions, psychology does not have any ‘restricted activities’ (activities that *only we* can perform) under the HPCA Act (2003). Similarly, most publishers of neuropsychological tests do not require you to hold registration as a neuropsychologist in order to use their products. Non-registered (academic) psychologists as well as pre-qualified interns regularly use cognitive neuropsychological tests and there is no suggestion that they are not qualified to do so.

Generally speaking, clinical psychologists should not be deterred from undertaking cognitive assessments, nor from practicing in fields that might be thought of as ‘neuropsychological’ (e.g. working with people with dementia); however, it is incumbent upon all psychologists that we remain aware of our own professional competencies and only practice within that range of knowledge (New Zealand Psychologists Board, 2018). If, as a registered psychologist, a piece of (neuropsychological) work is beyond your current level of competency, it is your duty to either

refuse that work or seek further advice and supervision (from a registered neuropsychologist) in order to undertake it a safe manner.

Summary and Conclusions

- Simple cognitive and psychometric assessment has long been a ‘core competency’ for clinical psychologists.
- As an example, the Board has clearly indicated that assessments of intellectual functioning and cognitive ‘screening’ are within the skill set of a (newly qualified) clinical psychologist.
- The Board’s competencies are ‘minimum standards’ for registration and it is certainly possible for clinical psychologists to exceed that basic level of knowledge.
- Neuropsychological knowledge exists on a spectrum, however those with the neuropsychologist scope will tend to have a much greater range of knowledge regarding:
 - appropriate test selection and interpretation
 - knowledge of a range of neurological conditions
 - understanding of cognitive neuropsychological rehabilitation
 - the work of other professions allied to neurology (e.g. neurologists, neuroradiologists, neurosurgeons).
- Where the reasons for neuropsychological consultation are more complex (e.g. requiring knowledge of neurological conditions, the reasons for poor cognitive functioning or recommendations for interventions), clinical psychologists are advised to either seek supervision and advice from their (clinical) neuropsychology colleagues, or refer directly to them.

References

- Health Practitioners’ Competency Assurance Act. NZ Parliament. (2003).
- The New Zealand Psychologists Board. (2022). *Consultation on the scope of practice for neuropsychology*. New Zealand Psychologists Board.
- The New Zealand Psychologists Board (2018). *Core competencies for the practice of psychology in Aotearoa New Zealand*. New Zealand Psychologists Board.
- Skirrow, P. M. (2020). Ka mua, ka muri-walking backwards into the future. *Journal of the New Zealand College of Clinical Psychologists*, 30(2), 3–6.
- Skirrow, P. M., Johnstone, G., Douglas, K., & Faulkner, J. (in preparation). Patterns of neuropsychological test usage amongst psychologists in New Zealand: Tests of memory. Submitted for publication to *The Clinical Neuropsychologist*, August 2022.